

The Coupling Constant Series and Curvature Absorptions – 8 Theory

O Manor

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Abstract:

By using the first representation of the coupling constant series, it is possible to construct a new equation that correlate the bosonic emissions to curvature propagations that get absorbed into the generator of the cyclic group. Such a framework that correlate between the bosons distribution across the Lorentz manifold to the amount of curvature the manifold has. By looking at electric fields for instance, it is possible to estimate the curvature of the manifold and the curvature variations.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (3.11)$$

$$(3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (3.12)$$

All of this was covered in previous papers. The majestic (3) is a generator of a cyclic group of bosonic net curvature propagations, isomorphic to the primes or one. We made a Feynman diagram using the new framework:

$$e \searrow \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow e \nearrow \quad (2.33)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.34)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (+5) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.35)$$

$$(+3) + N_V = (+3) + 5 = 8$$

$$8 = \text{even}$$

$$\text{even} = 0$$

The point of this paper is that in order to understand how the manifold vary, there are to be a summation of all curvature absorptions and emissions. As an electron absorb a photon, the manifold gets more flat, as $N_2 = +(5)$ just vanished into the electron and vice versa. By looking at clusters of photons in unit matrix, it is also possible to estimate how much curvature exits on the manifold. As bosons are net variations unbound, it was derived that preciously for that reason the probability of boson arrival after a boson is propagated.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i > 0 \quad (2.4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i > 0 \quad (2.41)$$

The point is, we can use space- time summation and in particular, the distribution of fermions to bosons to estimate how curved the matrix, or how it varies over time. It is vividly clear that a real world estimation is at the verge of impossible, but a rough evaluation is always within reach.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \gamma_i \rightarrow \mathcal{P}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{P}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial M}{\partial g}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{P}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

Equation (3.1) implies that the rate of change of photons over time is equivalent to the change in curvature in the metric. As photons are net curvature themselves. It was proved in March 2021 by deriving the coupling constants series from a varying Einstein manifold.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)